

A BRIEF HISTORY OF GERMAN LITERATURE**Jurayev Azizbek Anvarovich**

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Abstract: The term German-language literature or German literature refers to the literary works in German from the German-speaking area of the past and present. It begins with the Old High German Merseburg spells in the middle of the 8th century. In the broadest sense, the totality of all texts in the German language are counted among the German-language literature. According to a narrow concept of literature, German-language texts belonging to the major genres of drama, epic and poetry, as well as linguistically selected self-testimonies, including autobiographies, memoirs, diaries, letters, as well as essays, literary travel books, works of philosophy such as historiography and speeches with stylistic brilliance, are attributed to German-language literature.

Keywords: Competence, social competence, special competence, types of competencies.

Around the middle of the 12th century, literature became more diverse: topics that had previously been considered unworthy of writing were taken up. In addition, there were more different forms, such as courtly poetry, entertaining narratives. Spiritual poets took a new interest in individual people and their life stories, which led to legendary poems such as Albers Tundalus and Veldekes Servatius.

At that time, the one more secular (non-church) poetry also received a boost, namely the historical epic. She first came to prominence as a poet. The most important work, the Imperial Chronicle with around 17,000 verses, tells the story of the Roman Empire in episodes from the founding of Rome to Conrad III. The Song of Roland by the priest Conrad describes the battle of Charlemagne and his paladins against the Saracens in Spain as well as the death of Roland after a betrayal. With the Roland Song and the Alexander of the Priest Lamprecht, the influence of French fabrics and design

methods was also noticeable for the first time, which was to shape German-language literature for the next decades and centuries.

In the decades after 1150, a "heyday" of German-language literature dawned. At individual courts of the feudal nobility, a cultivated literary practice based on the Romanesque-language model spread: the so-called Courtly literature. In poetry, the Minnesang (high Minne) and the Sangspruch poetry developed, with their most important representatives Heinrich von Morungen, Reinmar the Old and Walther von der Vogelweide. For the courtly epic, even contemporaries considered the Enea novel by Heinrich von Veldeke, who came from the Lower Rhine to the Landgrafenhof in Thuringia and completed his work there around 1185, as the founding act. After that, numerous courtly epics in Middle High German were written based on French-language originals (Chrétien de Troyes). The most famous here are Erec and Iwein (Hartmann von Aue), Tristan and Isold (Gottfried von Strasbourg), Parzival (Wolfram von Eschenbach). Apart from this "modern" narrative culture, the anonymously transmitted heroic epic Nibelungenlied remains.

Early writers such as Niklas von Wyle or Heinrich Steinhöwel were particularly interested in translating new Latin texts of Italian humanism into German and sought to reform the German written language. Well-known representatives of the next generation were Conrad Celtis, Erasmus of Rotterdam, who worked in Basel, and Johannes Reuchlin, but they mostly wrote their works in Latin and initially had little influence outside the scholarly world and social elites. Anders Ulrich von Hutten (1488-1523) with his rebellious poems or Sebastian Brant (1458-1521), who wrote his successful *Narrenschiff* in German. Erasmus of Rotterdam's *Praise of Folly* is the most important work of German fool literature. Other works such as *Julius vor der geschlossenen Himmelstür* establish his position as the most important satirical author of his time. Another notable author of the 16th century is the Strasbourg Johann Fischart (1546-1590), his best-known work is the *Monkey-Theurlich Naupengeheurliche Geschichtklitterung*. Fischart was based on *Gargantua and pantagruel* by the Frenchman François Rabelais. A common genre of the time was the

folk book. It was created anonymously and was widely distributed because it took up popular topics. Examples are the *Historia* by D. Johann Fausten and the stories about Till Eulenspiegel. With the praise of folly, the latter is one of the most widely received prose texts of the early modern period.

In addition to humanism and the Reformation, the Meistersang, the Schwankdichtung and the Shrovetide play also deserve at least a mention, especially their best-known representatives, the Nuremberg Hans Sachs (1494-1576) and Jörg Wickram (around 1505 - before 1562). Since the 17th century, master singers have lost a lot of their reputation. Her poetry is regarded as the lowest point of German poetry in the bourgeois understanding of literature, which transfers a difference between art and rubbish or high and trivial literature to the literature of the past. Despite the interest of literary studies and the few benevolent voices on individual aspects of popular poetry, the poetry of the urban residents is considered a failure.

It is striking that – apart from Luther's song material and the Bible translation as a high-level linguistic transfer service, as well as Erasmus from Rotterdam's satire - German literature does not belong to the important European literature during the early Modern period or Renaissance. While in Italy poets such as Ludovico Ariosto and Michelangelo, the essayist Leonardo da Vinci, in France storytellers such as François Rabelais and the essayist Michel de Montaigne and in England Thomas More worked, the German authors mostly remained attached to older or trivial genres. Only Luther's contribution, which can hardly be overestimated as the nucleus of German Baroque literature, is an exception here. The strong importance of Baroque poetry over other genres such as the novel or the Baroque drama is an effect of its concentration on the song as a means of religious disciplining.

Poetry is taking things by storm and, not least because of the reception of the concept of genius, the one that ultimately refers to a voice of authority, in contrast to the discursive space of the theater or the novel, which is also addressed to a debating public, is of great breadth. Gottfried August Bürger, following Matthias Claudius, introduced the folk sound into German ballad poetry and can be considered the creator

of the ballad in the German language. For him, the ethics of genius does not lead to a conflict between genius and citizen, but leads to democratic convictions, according to which the artist, as a citizen in solidarity, becomes an accuser against the authorities and does not mobilize the outsider position of genius to save the subject. Precisely because he is an outsider, he can speak on behalf of the people. His poetry becomes the sharpest criticism of feudalism and arbitrary rule to date. Bürger's ballad art was to have a great influence on German ballad poetry, namely the Schillers and Goethes. Another poet was the journalist Christian Friedrich Daniel Schubart. However, the most important poetry besides Bürger's ballad poetry was created by the two poets Goethe and Schiller, who later worked together in Weimar.

Naturalism was a new art and literary trend that wanted to mercilessly expose the conditions in all spheres of society. What had been frowned upon as a topic by the realists of the middle of the century became the main subject of this literary direction. Regardless of the traditional limits of so-called good taste and bourgeois conceptions of art, excerpts of reality should be reproduced as far as possible in a congruence between reality and image. A major stylistic innovation was that colloquial speech, jargon and dialect were introduced. The individual hero, who can decide freely, is no longer at the center of the stories and dramas, but the person determined by a collective or by origin, milieu and circumstances of the time.

In Germany, Gerhart Hauptmann (1862-1946) became the most important representative of naturalism with his early and middle works. The play *Vor Sonnenaufgang* (premiere 1889) shows a peasant family the inevitability of social origin as well as the dissolution of the estates by capitalism.

Determinism, the addressing of social taboos, the use of dialect and the confrontation of different classes are naturalistic innovations that provoked the bourgeois public and were supposed to help Hauptmann to popularity. The *Weber* (premiere in 1894), a play written largely in the Silesian dialect, made Hauptmann known beyond Germany. The hero of the play is the Silesian weavers' uprising against entrepreneurship. The indifferent consideration of the uprising – the leader is

intoxicated – shifts due to the death of a skeptical weaver at least into the conceivability of the correctness of an uprising and led to the prohibition of a performance as well as to the interpretation of the ambivalent play as a revolutionary play. Other plays such as Fuhrmann Henschel, Der Biberpelz (premiere in 1893) and the play Rose Bernd (premiere in 1903) are milieu studies that partly connect to the social dramas of the Vormärz and realism, partly anticipate Expressionism through the communicative inability of the characters. The beaver fur is considered the strongest comedy of Hauptmann. Die Ratten (premiere 1911) was the last of Hauptmann's four major dramas. The tragicomedy from the late phase of German naturalism also foreshadows expressionism in its aesthetics of the ugly. As a milieu study, the Selicke family (first performance in 1890) by Arno Holz and Johannes Schlaf is often more radical than Hauptmann's Before sunset. While the closed form is abandoned dramaturgically by the station theater, concessions are made to the stirring piece in the constellation of characters and in the fate of the female characters. The work is considered an important document of naturalistic theater in Germany.,

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